

PROF. (DR.) YOGESH KUMAR

Ph.D, MSN, BSN, RNRM, DTSE

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Accredited by NAAC with Grade 'A'

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Career Objective

To pursue a career in any professionally managed organization, which would give me an opportunity to fully grow and use my potential to the fullest extent with sincerity and dedication.

Personal Strengths

Resourceful, Technical, Self-Confident, Good in Communication, Good in presentation, Analytical ability and Good understanding capability.

Professional Summary

- Focused academic professional seeking to leverage more than 19 years of educational experience.
- Well-versed in developing an engaging curriculum and presenting in both in-person and online formats.
- Expert in Cloud Computing, Cloud Data Handling, Basic Web development, and Graphic design.
- Acknowledged for Pediatric Nursing, Nursing Education, and Nursing Research.

Professional Qualifications

- Doctor of Philosophy (PhD): 2017-Mahatma Jyoti Rao Phoole University, Jaipur, Rajasthan.
- M.Sc. Nursing (Pediatrics): 2008-P.P.G. College of Nursing, Coimbatore, Tamil Nadu. The Tamil Nadu Dr. M.G.R. Medical University, Chennai, Tamil Nadu.
- B.Sc. Nursing: 2002-P.P.G. College of Nursing, Coimbatore, Tamil Nadu. The Tamil Nadu Dr. M.G.R. Medical University, Chennai, Tamil Nadu.

Additional Qualifications

- Diploma in "Teaching Skills for Educators".
- Certification Course in "Research Ethics".
- Certification Course "Introduction to Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis".
- Certification course "Instructional Methods in Health Professions and Education".
- Certification course and expert in Graphic Design and Basic Web development
- STC in "Intellectual Property Rights & Patenting in India" certified by NITTTR, Chandigarh.
- STC in "Classroom Communication in Digital Era" certified by NITTTR, Chandigarh.
- STC in "Outcome Based Curriculum Design" certified by NITTTR, Chandigarh.
- STC in "Evaluation and Setting of Question Papers" certified by NITTTR, Chandigarh.

Skills

- Expert and enthusiast in technology based education with a zeal in e-course development, graphic design and basic web development.
- Expert knowledge and skills in dealing with Intellectual Property Rights (IPRs).
- Member of Various Nursing Societies and Professional Associations.
- Extensive knowledge of Child Health Nursing, Nursing Education, Nursing Research, Nursing Administration and Management.
- Self-motivated
- Enthusiastic
- Culturally-sensitive
- Extremely organized
- Adult learning specialist
- Extremely Organized and detailed
- Strong public speaker
- Team liaison & leadership
- Identifying & Solving problems
- Staff development
- Fluent in English and Hindi and some other Local and National Languages.
- Compassionate
- Curriculum development
- Data management (offline & Cloud based)
- Best practices in on-line instruction
- Project management
- Course planning
- Adept at conflict resolution
- Strong verbal communication
- Conference Presentation & Public speaking ability
- Personable and approachable

Professional Achievements

- National Coach for Quality Improvement Certified by NQOCN.
- Master Trainer for “Development of MOOCs and Moodle based LMS” Certified by NIT, Kurukchetra.
- Master Trainer for “Simulation Methodology” Certified by NRSC in Collaboration with INC.
- Master Trainer for “Kangaroo Mother Care” Certified by KMC Foundation of India.
- Master Trainer for "Point of Care Quality Improvement" Certified by WHOCC and USAID.
- Master Trainer for "Hepatitis Updates & Induction Program" Certified by ILBS, New Delhi.
- Master Trainer for "HIV/AIDS and TB" under GFATM.

Awards and Recognitions

- "National Innovative Educator Award 2021" by the International Institute of organized Research (I2OR)
- "Rajya Puruskar Bharat-Scouts & Guides" by Governor Rajasthan in 1996
- Founder President, Women Child and Parents Foundation (WCPF)
- President Human Right Council Trust (HRCT), Doctor's Wing Haryana, India.
- National QI Coach and Core committee member under NQOCN.

Research Publications & IPRs

- Research Guide for Ph.D Nursing, Post graduate and undergraduate scholars.
- Published more than 60 research papers in Indexed and non-indexed journals.
- Presented Research papers at National and International conferences.
- Filed projects for funding under ICMR and DST-Haryana.
- Filed e-courses development at SWAYAM Portal.
- Filed Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) i.e. Patents (3), Copyrights(8)-Available under Public Domain License (CC-0)
- Published books (6), e-Books (3), Chapters and e-Value Added Courses (e-VACs)

Professional Roles & Job History

- Currently Designated as Professor at T.M. College of Nursing, a constituent of NAAC 'A' accredited Teerthanker Mahaveer University (TMU), Moradabad (UP).
- Working as Program Coordinator for PhD Nursing and also the Coordinator for IQAC at Teerthanker Mahaveer University.
- Worked as Professor Cum Ofg. Principal, Maharishi Markandeshwar Institute of Nursing.
- Worked as Professor cum HoD Pediatric Nursing and also chaired as an Officiating Principal at M.M.College of Nursing.
- Coordinated with Principal in daily operations in the field of Administration and Management.
- Chaired hiring committees for new core faculty members in the Department.
- Chaired the BoS and member of the Academic council and IEC.
- Member of the International Panel as Research Supervisor under Victoria University, Australia.
- Member of Reputed Committees and Panel of Examiners at various Institutions and Universities
- Being a Certified National QI-Coach under a Nationwide Quality of Care Network (NQOCN), Conducted in-services, Faculty Development Programs (FDPs) for teaching and clinical staff members.
- Conducted educational seminars, workshops and lectures at many Reputed and Govt. Institutions, i.e. PGI, CMC etc.
- As Trainer, conducted Many Lectures at Various Institutions under the GFATM Project.
- Handled Modular based Teaching under the Indian Association of Neonatal Nurses (IANN) i.e. ENBC and FBNC Modules.
- Chaired many students' thesis committees each year.
- Presented at Many conferences.
- Wrote course materials such as syllabi, homework assignments and handouts.
- Published multiple Research and Review articles in National and International journals.
- Reviewed many articles in various Reputed Indexed Journals.
- Integrated technology into classroom instruction for a well-rounded and modern approach by means of easy Smart Board Handling, Computing and online Resources like Google Apps and Cloud Computing.
- Enrolled in teaching, trainings & Guiding the Phd, Post-Graduate and undergraduate courses for Child Health Nursing, Nursing Education and Nursing Administration and Management.
- Selected appropriate materials to support student learning needs by adding e-Resources, Modules etc. (for advanced and slow learners)
- Worked with post-graduate and graduate students on classroom material and laboratory practicum.
- Recorded lessons for online instruction.
- Completed and submitted reports detailing course activities.
- Developed and implemented lesson plans that covered all required topics.
- Maintained office hours to help students with questions and educational support.
- Analyzed departmental documents for appropriate distribution and filing.

